
**PROBLEMS OF USING NATURAL-ECONOMIC POTENTIAL OF THE ARAL
SEAREGION (FOR EXAMPLE THE LOWER REACHES OF THE AMU
DARYA)**

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Abstract.

In the scientific article discusses the rational use of natural and economic potential in the context of improving the territorial organization of production economic areas Aral Sea region.

Keywords.

potential, intensification, specialization, acceleration, efficiency irrigation systems, resource, innovation, Agro-industrial complex.

In Lower reached Amudarii there is more than 23% irrigated land of the fund and more than 48% pasture facility of the Republic Uzbekistan. However, degree actual mastering irrigated lands forms lishi-2,5%. The Taken into accounted spares of iron ore 17 mlrd.tonn form in region Tebinbulak, cookery salt Barsakelmesbirthplace-14 mlrd.tonn, but spares borax coal 7,2 mlrd.tonn form in areas of water Aral epidemic deaths and etc. The Multiple openings new, including row unique birthplace natural gas, oils on Ustyurt,wizenedthe day Aral epidemic deaths completely provide the organizations an oil-gaschemical, metallurgical and others branches industrial production. However, mastering natural resource and development is given birth-economic complex Lower reached Amudarya is closely connected with decision many scientifically-applied on its nature economic, social, technical and the other problems both republican and regional scale. To their count;calculate;list it is necessary to refer the problems of the study Ustyurt and be of the bottom Arala, as well as irrigated land resource.

The Experience shows that without necessary source economic and geographical data, characterizing natural and social-economic ambience in territorial cut, impossible or is extremely labored development such project, as redistribution of the sewer Amudarya on branch facilities, making the large energy bases in zone of the production mastering Ustyurt. As well as, new centre to industry in zone influence to railway pathway Turtkul-Nukus-Kungrad-Beyneu

and others, which scientific provision requires the future direction of the economic mastering Northwest Uzbekistan as a whole. However, with using water of Amudarya in large quantity on irrigation upper and at the average his(its) current, intensive development production in Lower reached Amudarya become very difficult. The Much of the irrigated lands already presently subject to secondary for salting and grows worse the land reclamation condition of the lands. As a result, in Lower reached Amudarya appeared the complex ecological and social problems, having on level consequence the most harmful nature. Began the fall to productivities of the agricultural cultures, sharply changed the natural ambience and was thence saved up mass to negative ecological situation in all the Aral Modern level social-economic development and involvement natural-economic potential in economic turn in administrative region lower reached Amudarya is considered not sufficient. So for instance, region, disposing rich natural-raw materials resource, lags behind on production of the industrial product per capital in 1,4-1,5 with spare times less, than at the average on country. Moreover, industry of the region still has a nature of the primary conversion agricultural cheese and even in condition defect water resource.

The Territory lower reached Amudarya presents itself united production-territorial complex. This is connected with unity nationality problems them such as, united water problem, transport-telecommunication relationship, similarity agronomist specialization time for hydrodynamics to cycle production allows to consider him(it), as united economy-geographical region, which condition favour the organizations to general production specialization and creation all-round developed complex facilities type of the interstate free economic area. Considering these particularities of the region, it is necessary to spare emphases on making the base branches to industrial industry, as the most most important strategy of the speed development nationality complex whole lower reached Amudaryaregion.

Mastering natural resource and development are given birth-economic complex of the region is closely connected with decision many scientifically-applied on its nature economic, social and the other problems as the general republican, so and regional scale. To their count list it is necessary to refer the problems, making the large energy bases in zone of the mastering Ustyurt, new centre to industry and others, which scientific provision requires the future direction of the economic mastering the Aral region.

The other problems, is directly connected with migration of the population. The Known that before recent time for lower reached Amudarya were a typical

more complex processes of the moving the population. On the one hand, constant and all increasing need for artificer to power caused the influx a specialist, with other - an administrative regions lower reached Amudarya, in particular Karakalpakistan from year because of Aral crisis per annum, loses the big contingent of the population, besides most activity and able-bodied his(its) part. The Effect this is a defect of the skilled personelin different branch public facilities, in particular oil-chemical and gas industry. Intensive migration generates much difficulties in production and requires further, besides the most attentive dissidence studies of the development constructive and efficient ways of her(its) reduction. In connection with searching for of the ways of the fastening the personnel(frames) and making the happy circumstances for recovery social-economic life north region lower reached Amudarya appropriately to concern the question about place, scale and direction of the development of the new branches of the production complex.

On the general volume of the product industry in administrative region lower reached Amudarya at the beginning initially 2013 has formed 1 trillion 453,6 milliard sums that on 21,1 % more than in contrast with 2010. However she on rate of growth occupies amongst areas of the Republic of Uzbekistan one of the last places, and does not answer its raw materials and labor possibility. As a result in region irrational plant, plenty of types industrial product; this cotton wool and silk fabrics, chemical product, machines and equipment, refractory, ceramics, cement and other building materials; the paints, hardware. Regrettably, this problem possible was solve already presently on the base local raw materials resource In light said above, introduces expedient for instance, large centre oil-gas-chemical, ermine industrial with colour metallurgy, industrial bases agronomist cycle production, light industry and prolific.

Enormous value presents the decision of the problem of increasing drainageregion. From suitable to irrigation arable lands is presently irrigated only 522-524 thous. ga. So prospecting of additional water, in particular transfer of excessive water from zone Karakumchannel and Arnasay hydrophobiaurgent need becomes in pool Aral epidemic deaths. Together with this needs serious and urgent work to reconstructions are existing surd systems. Important increasing KPD irrigation systems introduces In this sense, selecting the agricultural cultures to condition lower reached Amudarya with reference to.

The Priority problem for mastering the new land in lower reached Amudarya, must become the first queue, irrigations north region, residing in zone of the influence Tahiatashhydrodynamics, where will be formed not only cotton-

luceme, but also multitapped territorial-production (agronomist) complexes. In economic attitude, much it is important development stock-breeding. Its role in salvaging biodeserted pasture and small labor content to branches wholly answer the permanent economic interest so it must save the important place in structure AIC administrative region Lower reached Amudarya.

Today development lousy and production power in lower reached Amudarya goes by creation and improvement of the different territorial production structures, up to agronomist complex. In this connection one of the problems is a development of the type agricultural enterprise and ways of the mastering natural-economic region for industrial integer upon the most essential directions.

One of their main of the directions scientifically exploratory searching for will is connected with problem of the organizations optimized territorial structure facilities, natural-economic region in Lower reached Amudarya. In this connection, in agrarian sector with provision for improvements agronomist cultivate agricultural cultures, introduction to enabling technologies waterfall, undertaking the capital planning by flap will is motivated irrigation rate watering that will allow to increase the irrigated area and enlarge the volume to product of the husbandry. In lying ahead prospect the furthest improvement to specialization and accommodations agricultural production in south region will go on way of the increase pat production-product in its raw state, silk cocoon, fruit and grape, as well as expansions of the area of the breeding karakul sheep. The Branches to industry, basically, will be based on conversion agricultural cheese.

The agronomist complex will get in central region speed development. In prospect sowings cotton plant do not enlarge, but branches to industry will develop, mainly, on conversion of the product APK, on production formation, is provided also development of the metalworking and machine building.

In north region alongside with intensity of the husbandry is expected intensive development зерноводства, grow vegetable of the cultures and stock-breeding, for what there are corresponding to condition. Besides, here in the near future appear the new centres petrochemical and gas industry. In Aral (Seaside) region, disposing enormous caughted pasture and fertile lands, is provided the most further development stock-breeding-meat of the milk direction and corn as well as oil tanker to industry. Thereby, involvement in economic turn new type cheese and industrial mastering reserve production, eventually, will promote shaping the branches to heavy industry on the base resource potential of the region. All this, certainly, will promote rational use an resource potential economic region, shaping

new centre production complex and industrial nodes, as well as populated points and making the systems of the regional settling for improvement of the living standard of the people inhabiting directly, in vicinity to epicentre of the Aral ecological crisis.

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